

Tracking of Rescue Workers in Harsh Indoor and Outdoor Environments ^{*}

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Abstract. Making use of reliable and precise location and tracking systems is essential to save firefighters lives during fire operations and to speed up the rescue intervention. The issue is that Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) (e.g., GPS and Galileo) is not always available especially in harsh wireless environments such as inside buildings and in dense forests. This is why GNSS technology needs to be combined with auxiliary sensors like inertial measurement units (IMU) and ultra-wideband (UWB) radios for ranging to enhance the availability and the accuracy of the positioning system. In this paper, we report our work in the scope of the AIOSAT (Autonomous Indoor/Outdoor Safety Tracking System) project, funded under the EU H2020 framework. In this project, the Royal Military Academy (RMA) is responsible for developing a solution to measure inter-distances between firefighters, based on IEEE Std 802.15.4 compliant UWB radios. For these inter-distance measurements, accuracy better than 50 cm is obtained with high availability and robustness. Medium access control based on time division multiple access (TDMA) mechanism is also implemented to solve the conflict to access the UWB channel. As a result, each node in a network can perform range measurements to its neighbors in less than 84 ms. In addition, in this project, we are in charge of developing a long-range narrow-band communication solution based on LoRa and Nb-IoT to report updated positions to the brigade leader and the command center.

Keywords: Location · Tracking · Firefighters · UWB RF-Ranging · LoRa · NB-IoT.

1 Introduction

Real time localization and tracking of fire responders is an important feature in rescue services management, in order to ensure the safety of the rescue workers and to accelerate the search and rescue process [1]. The satellite-based positioning technology, generally known as the global navigation satellite system

^{*} Results incorporated in this paper received funding from the European GNSS Agency under the European Unions Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 776425· Consortium: Ceit-IK4, ERM-KMS, SAXION, FRS Centrum, TSC.

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(GNSS), allows rescue workers to operate efficiently, however, the reliability and accuracy of such a system are often poor or absent during fire operations, at places like dense forests, underground parking, and inside buildings.

In this context, our work fits in the framework of an EU H2020 project named AIOSAT (Autonomous Indoor/Outdoor Safety Tracking System). The main objective of the project is to develop an integrated positioning and alerting system that aims to overcome aforementioned limitations of GNSS usage in rescue interventions in harsh signal propagation environments, and to improve the safety of first responders [2].

For this purpose, GNSS absolute position estimate is improved by the satellite-based augmentation system provided by the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay System (EGNOS). Furthermore, support of inertial measurement units (IMU) and radio frequency (RF) UWB ranging transceivers will be used to face GNSS-disadvantaged environments. Accordingly, GNSS positions are enhanced with EGNOS and fused with position information inferred from IMU sensors and range measurements from UWB radios, to provide high availability and high integrity positioning and tracking information of all members in a rescue team. A robust wireless communication system based on three technologies: LoRa standard, narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) and Bluetooth 5 (BT5) will be used to report calculated positions of the individual team members to the brigade leaders and to the coordination center.

The task of the Royal Military Academy (RMA) in this project is to develop an RF system based on IEEE Std 802.15.4 compliant UWB transceivers to measure inter-distances between the firefighters [3]. In addition, our task consists also in the development of the long-range communication system of the AIOSAT project, to allow sending position data to the intervention supervisors using LoRa and NB-IoT links. BT5 communication sub-system is implemented by another partner in the project. Each firefighter will be equipped with a portable AIOSAT module, including a GNSS receiver, an IMU sensor, and an UWB radio. These modules are controlled by a main processor, typically a Raspberry Pi that performs mainly the fusion algorithm and controls communication flows.

Nowadays, many real-time indoor localization systems (RTLS), based on UWB transceivers are commercially available, from companies like: Decawave, Ubisense, Time Domain, Zebra and Nanotran. Traditionally, the RTLS system consists of multiple fixed reference points, called anchor nodes, with known positions and mobile tags with unknown positions [4]. The tags try to estimate their positions relative to the anchors [5]. In the AIOSAT project, it would be impractical to set out anchor nodes. Therefore, we propose to implement, on the integrated UWB transceivers, a ranging scheme to measure inter-distances between freely moving UWB nodes, without a need for fixed reference nodes. This inter-distance information can then be used to enhance the estimated positions of the portable AIOSAT modules. A time division multiple access (TDMA) mechanism is also implemented to control the UWB medium access. This medium

access mechanism is important to schedule the time slots relative to the different devices in the network to perform their ranges estimate.

In this project, we used DW1001 miniaturized UWB transceivers from Decawave on which we implemented our ranging scheme. This device has an IEEE Std 802.15.4-2011 compliant radio (DW1000), and a microcontroller from Nordic Semiconductor (nRF52832) [5], [6]. Tests results of range measurements between first responders developed using these devices are discussed in this paper.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the architecture of the distributed AIOSAT system, Section 3 describes the RF-UWB ranging principle, the implemented scheme, and the scheduling mechanism. In Section 4, the experimental results of the UWB ranging system are presented and discussed. And finally, Section 5 describes the IoT communication solution and gives some field tests results and concluding remarks.

2 Architecture

2.1 Distributed System Architecture

On the next page, Fig. 1 represents the system level architecture of the AIOSAT system, which is designed in order to meet the user requirements. The rescue intervention is composed of few fire trucks staffed with 4 firemen, one fireman driver, and one brigade leader. They are supervised by a mobile coordination center (MCC). Each firefighter is equipped with an integrated AIOSAT module, composed of a GNSS receiver, an IMU and an UWB transceiver. The gathered data, from the three sensor systems, is locally processed at the level of the firefighters to give enhanced position estimates. The estimated positions are reported to the brigade leader and the MCC that are in charge of the coordination and control of the rescue operation. They are equipped with a visualization tool for the real-time tracking of moving resources. Estimated positions are sent using one of the two communication links (LoRa, NB-IoT) [2]. Downlink alert messages sent from higher levels to firefighters are also supported by this architecture.

2.2 Portable AIOSAT Module Architecture

In order to enhance the accuracy and availability of firefighters positions, their locations are measured from three types of sensors: GNSS, IMU, and UWB transceivers. The data of each sensor is locally published to a broker using the MQTT publish-subscribe based messaging protocol, then a fusion algorithm process those inputs to provide enhanced estimated positions that are sent over communication links to the team leaders and the MCC. This process is presented in Fig. 2 [2]. Our contribution in this project are following:

- Inter-distance ranging between firefighters in indoor environments measured using RF UWB technology. Firefighters are equipped with UWB transceivers that compute the range between them based on the time of flight (ToF) of exchanged packets.

Fig. 1. Distributed AIOSAT system architecture.

- The transfer of enhanced positions from the firefighters to the brigade leader and to the MCC is ensured using either LoRa technology or NB-IoT if coverage is available [7].

Fig. 2. AIOSAT portable module architecture.

3 RF-Ranging Principle

A promising positioning solution for areas with poor or no GNSS coverage, typically indoor environments, is to make use of RF-based UWB technology [3]. The principle is to estimate the ToF of exchanged RF signals between UWB transceivers from which we can derive ranging information. A symmetrical double-sided two-way ranging (SDS-TWR) scheme is used to estimate this ToF.

3.1 Symmetrical Double-sided Two-way Ranging

The mechanism relies on time-stamping the instances when a packet leaves the transmitter and arrives at the receiver measured according to their own clocks. Fig. 3 describes the messaging sequence that we applied for range measurement initiated by node i to all its 1-hop neighbors based on the SDS-TWR scheme. This ranging process is preceded by a phase of neighborhood discovery using so-called *hello* packets in order to draw up a list of 1-hop neighbors of a node. The SDS-TWR scheme relating two or more nodes is organized as follows:

- Node i starts by broadcasting a ranging request packet called *probe* to all its neighbors. This packet includes the beforehand carried out neighbors list.
- When receiving this *probe* packet, each UWB node that finds itself in the neighbors list sends a *response* packet after waiting a certain delay relative to its position on the list, that is to make the neighbors respond in a certain order. Although, those delays are dictated by the node i in its communicated neighbors list, they are measured independently according to each neighbors own clock.
- After sending *probe* packet, node i waits a predetermined time (c) relative to an estimation of the required waiting time to receive *response* packets from the last neighbor in the list, then it broadcasts the second packet called *feedback*.
- Upon receiving the *feedback* packet by the 1-hop neighbors, they reply by sending *report* packets where they include timestamps for receiving *probe* and *feedback* packets, and transmitting *response* and *report* packets. this allows the node i to estimate the ToF of the exchanged packets and thus to deduce the distances that separate it to each neighbor. The neighbors send *report* packets in an inverse order to the one used for sending *response* packets. With this order reversal, we have symmetrical delays between receiving the *feedback* ($T_{rx,j}^f$) and sending the *response* packet ($T_{tx,j}^{rs}$) by a neighbor node j from one side and receiving the *report* packet from that node ($T_{rx,j}^{rp}$) and sending the *feedback* packet by node i from the other side ($T_{tx,i}^f$). In this way, a symmetry is also applied between the delay between sending the *feedback* packet ($T_{tx,i}^f$) and receiving the *response* ($T_{rx,j}^{rs}$) from neighbor j in one side, and the delay between sending the *report* ($T_{tx,j}^{rp}$) and receiving the *feedback* packet ($T_{rx,j}^f$) from that neighbor, in the other side. Therefore, a precise estimation of the ToF and thereby of the range is guaranteed.

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- Node i estimates the ToF to a neighbor node j , after receiving the corresponding *report* packet, as given by (1) [15].

$$t_{ToF} = \frac{(T_{rx,j}^f - T_{tx,j}^{rs}) - (T_{tx,i}^f - T_{rx,j}^{rs})}{4} + \frac{(T_{rx,j}^{rp} - T_{tx,i}^f) - (T_{tx,j}^{rp} - T_{rx,j}^f)}{4} \quad (1)$$

The main optimization that we introduced to the original SDS-TWR scheme results in a reduced number of exchanged packets compared to the typical or classical implementation of the SDS-TWR. When ranging with k neighbors, our scheme requires $2 + 2k$ packets whereas the classical SDS-TWR would require $3k$ packets to do the ranging with the same number of nodes. This reduction in the packets is achieved by broadcasting *probe* and *feedback* packets to k neighbors, compared to the classical implementation where range measurement is done pairwise—in which case one *probe* packet and one *feedback* packet are required per node-pair. In addition, we reduce the error in the ToF estimation by reversing the order of sending *report* packets by the neighbors compared to the order of sending *response* packets. This ensures an accurate range estimate. With the ToF estimate and knowing the propagation speed of the RF signal, node i can estimate the range to all its 1-hop neighbors.

Fig. 3. Packet sequence exchange in SDS-TWR with 1-hop neighbors.

3.2 Performances

We need to minimize the ToF estimation error in order to enhance the accuracy of the calculated range between UWB radio nodes. The error in ToF estimate, and thereby in the range estimate, depends on the precision of the crystal oscillators driving the clocks of the nodes, and the waiting time between receiving a packet and transmitting the corresponding reply, as in (2) [3].

$$e \approx \frac{1}{4}(\tau_{j,i} - \tau_{i,j})(\epsilon_i - \epsilon_j). \quad (2)$$

Where e denotes the estimation error in ToF for SDS-TWR, assuming both participating nodes remain static. The drifts on the clocks of the two ranging nodes are denoted by ϵ_i and ϵ_j . We can see that the error in ToF estimate for SDS-TWR, is proportional to the difference in $\tau_{i,j}$ and $\tau_{j,i}$, which denotes the waiting times between receiving a packet and sending the corresponding *response* packet for given node i and its neighbor j , respectively (c.f., Fig. 3). The delay depends on the packet airtime, radio turnaround time, and required time to process the ranging packet. Note that, these waiting times are on the order of a few milliseconds, while their difference $\tau_j - \tau_i$ can be easily controlled to the order of a few tens of microseconds using low stability commodity clocks. It is important to notify that the timestamps are captured close to the physical layer, consequently, the jitter is minimal. For example, for a difference of waiting times between two ranging UWB nodes of 100 μ s, with clocks drift of 8 parts per million (ppm), we have an error on the ToF estimate of about 0.2 ns. Knowing that, for a target ranging accuracy of 33 cm, the estimated ToF needs to lie within 1 ns of the true ToF given the speed of light. We can conclude, that the SDS-TWR can provide required ranging accuracy despite significant clock errors. Note that each 1-hop neighbor will include also, its own estimated position, in the *response* packet that it sends to node i , as this will be needed by node i to estimate its own position based on the inter-distance measurements.

3.3 Medium Access Control Technique

To support conflict-free measurements using the UWB link, it is important to use a scheduling mechanism. To this end, we implemented a TDMA medium access control mechanism, where the transmissions of the different UWB nodes in a neighborhood, are arranged in respective time slots within a periodic frame. In each allocated time slot, the corresponding node performs ranges estimate to all its neighbors. We chose to use 1 pulse per second (PPS) signal to synchronize the UWB frames. We get the PPS signal from the GNSS receiver included in the AIOSAT module as presented in Fig. 2. The results of implementation and tests of this synchronization scheme show that each UWB module performs ranging with up to 11 neighbors within a TDMA slot of 83.33 milliseconds. Therefore, 12 UWB nodes can perform range estimate to each other in their corresponding time slots in a frame of 1 second.

4 Experimental Results of the RF-Ranging system

We want to reduce the duration of the ranging sequence presented in Fig. 3. To this end, we need to reduce the size of the exchanged packets. The packet airtime can be reduced by decreasing the preamble length (number of symbols) and increasing the data rate. Tests are required to assess the influence of these two parameters on the ranging performance in terms of success rate of ranging sessions, and accuracy and precision of range measurements. We assume that a ranging session has succeeded when all packets needed to be exchanged are properly received, see Fig. 3, and we are able to calculate the distance. For each of the tests that we will discuss in this section, we conducted a set of 1000 measurements and out of that we counted the number of the succeeded ranging sessions. This number out of the total attempted sessions gives us the ranging sessions success rate.

To this end, we have used Decawave DWM1001 UWB transceivers to implement our modified SDS-TWR algorithm that provides range measurements between an initiating UWB node and its dynamically discovered neighbors. These devices support 7 frequency channels among 16 channels provided by the IEEE 802.15.4 standard and 4 different bandwidths [3], [5]. For the tests, we configure the transceivers to operate on channel 5 [6240 - 6739.2 MHz] for which the integrated antenna on the DW1001 module is tuned [5]. Decawave gives the possibility to configure its devices on three different data rates (110 kb/s, 850 kb/s and 6.8 Mb/s), and 7 different preamble lengths (64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096) [6]. In fact, the sensitivity of the DW1000 radio improves as we go from the highest data rate to the lowest available one [14]. Moreover, the choice of the preamble length affects the ability of the receiver to detect the incoming signal in the noise [14].

We conducted a series of tests for different radio parameters (e.g., data rate and preamble), and in different locations (e.g., outdoor, indoor). For each test setup, we collected 1000 range measurements which enable us to compute descriptive statistics of the results (e.g., ranging session success rate, average range, and standard deviation of the measured range). With these descriptive statistics we characterize the performances of the implemented ranging algorithm. By decreasing the data rate and increasing the preamble length, it is expected that the UWB communication reliability and operational range will improve in free space line-of-sight (LoS) scenario [6]. Nevertheless, this leads to an increase in the packet airtime, with corresponding increase in the required time to conclude a range session, and consequently increases error in range estimation. Based on the test results we find that we need to make a trade-off between the availability and the precision of the ranging on one side and the range session duration on the other side.

We conducted the first set of tests in an outdoor environment with LoS. The main objective of these tests is to identify the maximum operational range that can be achieved for different configurations of data rates and preamble lengths as resumed by Table 1. In order to look for the maximum achievable range, we increase progressively the separating distance between the UWB transceivers

and we stop at a threshold of ranging sessions success rate that we fixed at 80 %. Success rate, mean range and standard deviation have been depicted in Fig. 4. From the figure we can find that the range sessions success rates is always better than 80 % for all the tests. The mean range is calculated as the average value over all the range measurements. We also measured the systematic error for these sets of tests as given in Table 1. The systematic error represents the error between the measured distance and the actual distance measured manually using a laser range finder. The systematic errors are mainly caused by antenna delays [15], [16]. Therefore, transceiver calibration is required to eliminate this error. Consequently, further better accuracy are expected on the range estimate [15].

Fig. 4. Success rate, mean range and standard deviation of measurements in outdoor tests for various data rates and preamble lengths.

It is important to note that in outdoor open spaces, the most common form of multipath is caused by RF reflections from the ground that can interfere constructively or destructively (causing fading) with the direct path signal at the receiver [14]. For this reason, we need to take this fading effect into consideration before we start recording the measurements. We can see from Fig. 4 that the standard deviation remains less than 8 cm. We can also notice that the highest maximum range, which is 80 m, is reached as we operate with the lowest data rate (110 kb/s) combined with the highest preamble length (1024). The maximum operational range achieved for a data rate of 850 kb/s is also important (between 70 and 73 m) which is sufficient for AIOSAT system requirements. What is also

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Fig. 5. Success rate, mean range and standard deviation of measurements in indoor tests with a fixed distance of 70 m and for various data rates and preamble lengths.

Table 1. Summary of outdoor tests for different data rates and various preamble lengths.

Data rate	110 kb/s			
Preamble length	1024	512	256	128
Average range (m)	80	73	77	62
Average systematic error (cm)	42	38	36	37
Data rate	850 kb/s			
Preamble length	1024	512	256	128
Average range (m)	70	73	70	72
Average systematic error (cm)	27	38	23	25
Data rate	6.8 Mb/s			
Preamble length	1024	512	256	128
Average range (m)	36	35	37	37
Average systematic error (cm)	41	45	43	42

interesting in this data rate is that the maximum range does not vary more than 3 cm for the 4 different preamble lengths, moreover, the standard deviation is limited to 3.2 cm for a preamble length of 256.

Using this combination of data rate and preamble length (850 kb/s and 256) can provide us a good operational range and accuracy for AIOSAT ranging subsystem. We can see in Table 2 that the systematic error for this configuration is lowest (23 cm) compared to the other data rates and preamble lengths combinations. This configuration is preferred to the first one (a data rate of 110 kb/s and a preamble length of 1024) because the airtime of the frame is lower and so is the range session duration. For example for the *report* packet which is the longest one with 44 bytes payload, the airtime is estimated at 0.65 ms for 850 kb/s and 256, compared to 4.13 ms for 110 kb/s of data rate and 1024 of preamble length. We can assume from Fig. 4 and Table 1 that we need to give up the option of operating at 6.8 Mb/s for the AIOSAT project, due to its lowest maximum range (less than 37 m) and its high systematic error (more than 41 cm).

In addition to these outdoor experiments, we also conducted tests inside a building where we positioned the two UWB nodes in a corridor of more than 80 m long with a LoS. In this typical indoor environment maximum range that can be achieved is expected to be larger to the quoted for outside free space, because on top of the ground reflection we have additional multi-path reflections from walls that give extra usable receive signal [6]. Fig. 5 presents the results of indoor tests for different configurations of data rates and preamble lengths. In this case, the separation between the two nodes is fixed at a distance of 70 m. Success rate, mean range and standard deviation are presented in Fig. 5. We can see that the range sessions success rate remains higher than 77 % for data rates of 110 and 850 kb/s for the different preamble lengths. The standard deviation stays less than 5 cm for all cases in the figure except for the configuration of 850 kb/s data rate and 128 preamble length where the standard deviation reaches as much as 1.1 m. This latter combination is excluded from use in the AIOSAT project. The ranging success rate is very low (less than 25 %) for a data rate of 6.8 Mb/s with preamble lengths of 1024 and 512. For this data rate combined with a preamble length of 128, the standard deviation is very high (about 60 cm), so we exclude these last combination too. We can use a data rate of 6.8 Mb/s combined with a preamble length of 256 where the success rate is about 70 %. To conclude, considering the tests results performed in outdoor environment for maximum operational ranges, and the experiments results conducted in indoor with fixed distance, and with a concern to minimize the UWB frame airtime and consequently the range session duration, we assume that the combination that fits more to this compromise is the one with 850 kb/s data rate and 256 preamble length.

5 Communication System

The transfer of firefighters computed positions is ensured using long range communication links (LoRa and NB-IoT). We have established on computer a private LoRa network based on an open-source implementation of LoRaWAN network server [8].

The firefighters are equipped with LoRa end-devices from Pycom (FiPy) [9]. For NB-IoT connectivity, FiPy module can be used with a SIM card that provides access to the NB-IoT network. Bidirectional LoRa communication is implemented on Pycom class-A end devices. LoRa uplink communication serves to send updated firefighters positions to the brigade leader and the MCC. Over-the-air authentication is used by the end devices to join the LoRa network. We also implemented the Listen Before Talk Adaptive Frequency Agility (LBT AFA) protocol to access LoRa frequency channels; in order to avoid the end device transmit duty cycle limitation of 1% imposed by the ETSI regulations [10], and to lower the risk of collisions. LoRa downlink communication has also been implemented in order to send alert messages from LoRa network to Pycom devices. A MultiConnect Conduit IP67 gateway is used to relay messages between end devices and the central LoRa local Network at the backend [11]. It is attached to the light pole of the firefighters truck and connected via Ethernet to the local network as presented in Fig. 6. It forwards the received messages from the end-devices to the LoRa server. This gateway is dedicated for outdoor environments and it supports LTE back haul capabilities [11]. In some scenarios, we can use more than one gateway in a rescue intervention, all forwarding packets to the same local network server. Transmitted messages in this case can be received by all gateways, where duplicated packets are removed by the LoRa server.

Fig. 6. Field test setup of LoRa communication.

When NB-IoT coverage exists, FiPy devices are configured to send data using NB-IoT uplink to the operator server. In rescue interventions in Belgium, we use orange network [13]. Field tests of LoRa and NB-IoT communications have been performed in an underground parking in Ghent, Belgium, in collaboration with the fire station center of Ghent (FRS Centrum). The goal is to test the

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Fig. 7. LoRa tests in a parking Scenario.

communication system in a critical underground fire scenario. This parking is situated in the center of Ghent, which is an old construction composed of 3 levels in the underground. Fig. 7 presents the tests results in terms of SNR and RSSI of LoRa communication using FiPy devices with spreading factors of 10 and 11. We chose these high spreading factors to make the demodulation of received packets possible even with very low SNR [12]. For the tests we sent packets using sequence numbers as a useful data with an interval of 12 seconds. This sequence number is used to track the successfully transmitted packets and the lost ones. The success rate of transmitted packets from the -3 level to the gateway placed on a firefighter truck at the entrance of the parking is of 50% with a spreading factor of 11. NB-IoT communication have also been tested in this parking but the communication was bad. We could not transmit packets successfully from -3 level. So for this critical scenario, we prefer to use LoRa communication solution for sending estimated positions of the rescue workers to the command center.

6 Conclusion

The aim of the AIOSAT tracking and alerting project is to exploit the positioning, ranging and communication subsystems to develop an application that provides mobile situational awareness. Members positions, inter-distances, and other sensor information are fused to give enhanced position estimates and alerting functionality supporting the decision-making and safety operations of the mission members. In this paper, we reported our work on developing the RF-UWB ranging sub-system to measure the inter-distances between firefighters. Experiments in outdoor and indoor scenarios have been conducted and discussed in order to characterize the influence of relevant parameters such as the data rate

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and the preamble length, on the ranging performances in terms of availability, accuracy, and precision. Furthermore, a long-range communication system based on LoRa and NB-IoT has been implemented and results from field tests in a critical underground fire scenario have been presented in this paper.

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